
**The Limits of Structures: A Shorter Version of a Comparison between
Toni Morrison's *Song of Solomon* and Virginia Hamilton's *M. C. Higgins the Great***

Someone who accidentally read *Song of Solomon* as a children's novel or *M. C. Higgins, the Great* as an adult once might not be terribly surprised. Not only are they similar to each other, but *Song of Solomon* has qualities usually ascribed to children's fiction, qualities *M. C. Higgins* lacks. And as Jonathan Culler says, the meaning of literary texts resides less in the words they contain than in "the intent at totality of the interpretative process: the strength of the expectations which lead readers to look for certain forms of organization in a text and to find them."¹ Nevertheless, readers have fastened on the adult qualities of the children's novel and the childlike qualities of the adult one as the most noteworthy things about them. A critic suggests the unusual narrative stance of *M. C. Higgins* "can become a problem for the young reader, who is used to, and has a tighter hold on, a more usual narrative form . . . ,"² and a reviewer of *Song of Solomon* says its grisly events

"are nearly deprived of their grisliness by the tone. It might be a folktale . . . ,"³ a form usually considered appropriate for children. These readers had expectations which these novels did not meet. I suspect someone who did read *M. C. Higgins* as an adult novel or *Song of Solomon* as one for children would still concentrate on their variance from the expected norm. The fact that one was written for children and one was not makes them markedly unlike each other.

"The father may soar/And the children may know their names";⁴ the epigraph of *Song of Solomon* suggests themes which also appear in *M. C. Higgins*, but to quite different effect. In both novels, young black men feel blocked by their fathers. Milkman Dead more or less rejects his father; *M. C. Higgins* eventually accepts his. But Milkman must deny his father because his values are contemporary,

urban, and white; M. C. must accept his father because his values are traditional, rural, and black—the values Milkman also accepts. I believe the different ways the two arrive at the same conclusion derive from our ideas about the difference between childhood and maturity. Since we believe that children want to rebel against parental values, we like to tell them they will gain maturity by perceiving their parent's worth; adults, who have accepted mature values, sometimes see them as “shades of the prison-house” that blot out the light of their childhood innocence. As the protagonist of a children's novel, M. C. finds happiness in becoming mature; as the protagonist of an adult novel, Milkman learns that his supposed maturity must be reconsidered.

Both novels associate childhood innocence with the past, and with traditional black culture. But *Song of Solomon* seems to reject contemporary white civilization, while *M. C. Higgins* tries to balance past and present, black and white, freedom and constraint. *M. C. Higgins* creates a complex balance between the values it first opposes, while *Song of Solomon* works at replacing one clearcut set of values with another. Milkman learns to trust simplicity, while M. C. must learn that things are more complicated than he thought. We might be surprised that the adult novel has a more simple resolution than the children's novel. We might be especially surprised that the novel for grownups values the childlike more wholeheartedly than the novel for children. But we do believe that children, who egocentrically adhere to the only interpretation of reality they know, need to learn compromise—a consciousness of others. Children's novels about children of all colours frequently end as *M. C. Higgins* does, with their protagonists' awakening realizations of their previous egocentricity; in children's novels, even black children have to grow up. Meanwhile, many adult novels concern their protagonists' unegocentric understanding of the real complexities of living with others—their lack of childish certainty. Since we value that certainty to the extent that we do not have it, literature written for adults inevitably values the childlike more than children's literature does.

Consequently, children's novels tend to have a different structural focus than adult ones. Since children's novels typically end with their protagonists' discovery of new values, they are often shaped like traditional quests. The protagonist leaves the security of home, or like M. C. Higgins, the security of childlike perception, and discovers a larger world outside. He returns home wiser; but since he does return home, he must fit together his old ideas and his new ones, and in doing so, realize the ambiguity of maturity. This is the “circular journey”⁵ which Jon Stott sees as a basic pattern of children's literature. Meanwhile, adult novels tend to be less quests for something different than analyses of life as it is already; characters who understand that there's no place *not* like home learn more about themselves where they already are. They do that by ex-

ploring the meaning of their experiences, and Jonathan Culler suggests that such explorations form patterns of binary opposites: “when two things are set in opposition to one another the reader is forced to explore qualitative similarities and differences, to make a connection so as to derive meaning from the disjunction.”⁶ Since the meaning emerges from confusion—the ambiguity of maturity—the connections of resolution have a comparative simplicity, like the simplicity Milkman learns.

To generalize wildly: in children's books, things get better by getting more complex; in adult books they get better by getting less complex, more understandable. Children's books describe loss of innocence, adult books attempt to regain it. Because we believe that children grow up, children's fiction almost always assumes that things can and do change in time; the situation can improve. But adults have grown up already, so adult fiction tends to imply that nothing can or will change but one's knowledge about or attitude toward what already is. Time evolves in children's fiction, merely passes in adult fiction. Since children's books move out of egocentricity toward maturity, the question that shapes them is an old one: what will happen next? Will M. C. leave the mountain? Will Jones? Will M. C.'s mother get a recording contract? Will the spoil heap fall? While most adult novels do not ask the opposite question with the intensity of *Song of Solomon*, they usually imply it: what happened? what brought us to this pass? *Song of Solomon* moves forward by moving back—by finding explanations in the past for circumstances in the present.

C. S. Lewis once said that writing a children's novel ‘compels one to throw all the force of the book into what was done and said. It checks what a kind but discerning critic called ‘the expository demon’ in me.’⁷ Like Lewis, most readers expect children's novels to tell a story above all else, to be organized as a series of unified actions—to have a plot; and we tend to expect adult novels to be filled with exposition, to be organized around *explanations* of what their events mean—to have a theme based on binary opposites. If Culler is right about expectations, we will find exactly what we want—and indeed, *M. C. Higgins* does offer a plot that focusses our attention on what will happen next, and *Song of Solomon* a set of binary opposites that provide explanations.

But the plot of *M. C. Higgins* is not very satisfying. When I taught this novel to students of children's literature, they disliked it, not just because so little happens in it, but because it thwarted their expectations of what might happen. It was not about a circus or a superhero, as the title led many of them to expect. M. C. does not fly; he does not even try and fail. M. C.'s mother does not become a recording star. M. C. meets a girl he likes, but she leaves without resolving his confusion about her. The spoil heap does not fall, nothing happens to prevent it from falling,

and it is not shown conclusively that it will never fall; there is no confrontation with the strip miners. According to my students, the novel frittered away its opportunities for satisfying action amidst a welter of what they called “descriptions”; they saw it as a boringly overdetailed travelogue, a day in the life of M. C. Higgins.

The binary opposites to be found in *Song of Solomon* are not as unsatisfactory as the plot of *M. C. Higgins*; a close reading showed me how they organize the novel and make it meaningful. My desire to read it closely was a response to its power, a way of coping with the exhilaration my first reading evoked. But my close reading, while interesting in itself, merely replaced exhilaration with explanation, and so does not account for the exhilaration. A discussion of the plot of the novel in terms of how it excites attention and creates involvement might begin to do that. But the binary opposites that explain events in *Song of Solomon* no more completely describe the novel than a summary of the plot describes *M. C. Higgins* as a whole. Despite our expectations that the children’s novel tell a story and that the adult one have meaning, both of these novels offer something more, something that should perplex careful readers and demand further attention.

At one point, Hamilton tells us that M. C. Higgins is “overcome by the power of two separate thoughts”;⁸ in fact, her entire novel consists of a clear and careful counterpointing of opposed separate thoughts and images, centering around leaving and staying, freedom and constraint, growing up and staying young, tradition and modernity, past and future. My own literary training allows me to see such binary opposites with ease, and I had no trouble in finding them (usually embedded in what my students called descriptions) or in describing them to my students, in an attempt to make them appreciate the novel more. But my discussion did nothing to change their minds; if *they* needed help to understand it, they said, then what hope was there for mere children? Limited by their own structural expectations, they assumed children shared them, and rejected a book that did not meet them.

In terms of sheer action, *Song of Solomon* has a more obviously exciting plot than *M. C. Higgins*; the book could easily be read as the “circular journey” we expect of children’s fiction. Its young protagonist fights with his parents, leaves the security of a restrictive home in search of gold, and has exciting encounters with unusual people in strange locales; finally he discovers the secret he was unwittingly seeking, and as the quest pattern leads us to expect, returns home wiser. While such a description of *Song of Solomon* leaves out much of significance, it is not inaccurate; and the book *is* exciting and suspenseful.

When I taught *Song of Solomon* to a group of English majors a few weeks after my experience with *M. C. Higgins*, I was not surprised that they enjoyed the novel. But they

were so busy ferreting out its meaning that they seemed not to have noticed that anything had happened in it at all. Like my children’s literature students, these English majors were limited by their limited expectations of structure. My experience in teaching *M. C. Higgins* had made me so conscious of their silence on the subject of plot that I asked them about it. They agreed it was exciting, and that it held their attention completely; but beyond that they could say nothing. Their training as students of literature had rendered them incapable of discussing any sort of literary structure but binary opposites; they had no language to describe a large part of their experience of the book.

The novel had another quality they could not deal with, which they called “magic”; but they were bothered by it enough to talk about it extensively. Since *Song of Solomon* begins with explanatory details like the reason for the name of Not Doctor Street, my students had started to read it as a realistic novel. But then things happened that are not only unexplained, but unexplainable—including Milkman’s eventual attempt at flight. Morrison even annoyingly insists on their inexplicability. When she speaks of “an odor like crystallized ginger” (p. 184) that comes from the lake and makes people conscious of what they lack, she insists, “There is no explanation for the odor either.” My English majors were just as disturbed by the moments of fantasy in a primarily realistic novel as were my children’s literature students by the apparent excess of description in *M. C. Higgins*; and they calmly accepted the sort of discussion of the novel’s binary opposites that had merely confirmed my children’s literature students’ dislike of *M. C. Higgins*. Limited by their structural expectations, my students could cope neither with the childlike qualities of the adult novel nor the theoretically adult qualities of the children’s novel.

Even worse, they could not see how these novels, which both have carefully constructed plots and carefully constructed patterns of binary opposites, fit those two structures together. An analysis of plot by itself, which merely maps out how a book excites attention, cannot suggest what readers should give their attention to once it has been excited. An analysis of binary opposites by themselves cannot explain how a novel makes us care about its theme, or even how meaning evolves from events. Patterns of binary opposites are purely two-dimensional until they resolve, and Frank Kermode rightly condemns “the questionable literary practice of calling literary structure *spatial*. We can distribute our fictions in time as well as in space, which is why we must avoid an easy translation from the one to the other.”⁹ Since novels must combine the spatial order of binary opposites with the temporal order of events, a discussion of one is incomplete without a discussion of the other. It was only when my students’ responses to these novels made me realize that and I tried to see how the two structures fit together in both novels that I began to realize how richly and intricately constructed they both are.

To sum up what I found: *Song of Solomon* moves through a series of deepening, progressively longer, and more meaningful voyages into the past, until Milkman Dead finally discovers his heritage in a long last thrust backward that causes him to lose both his urban, white clothes and his urban, white values. *M. C. Higgins* is constructed like a symphony in three movements, each following the same pattern but establishing a different mood and exploring a different aspect of the same central questions. The first movement presents clearcut oppositions, the second muddies them and shows their ambiguities, and the third resolves them; each movement occurs on a different day in M. C.'s life, and each comments on the others by establishing parallels between quite different events, people, and images.

In fact, both *Song of Solomon* and *M. C. Higgins* express their meaning exactly and most completely through the carefully chosen sequencing of their events. Despite the instructive way in which they express the limitations of the genres they belong to, both move past those limitations—but only for readers willing and able to see that. If we limit ourselves to patterns of binary opposites that resolve without ever evolving, we lose both the pleasure of stories for their own sake and the more satisfying perception of *how* stories make events meaningful. Even more sadly, our nostalgic conviction that the innocence of childhood is an unmixed blessing to be preserved at all cost lets us persuade ourselves that children need and can comprehend nothing more in literature than the pleasure of stories for their own sake; it also lets us deprive children of most of the true rewards of fiction. If perception of structural patterns is a learned competence, there is no reason why human beings of any age should not be taught it. Furthermore, parents and teachers who care enough about both children and literature to teach them that competence soon discover that children are eminently capable of learning it.

Perry Nodelman
Department of English
University of Winnipeg

NOTES

¹*Structuralist Poetics: Structuralism, Linguistics and the Study of Literature* (Ithaca, New York: Cornell, 1975), p. 91.

²Kathleen Scholl, "Black Traditions in *M. C. Higgins, the Great*," *Language Arts* 47, 4 (April, 1980), 420.

³Diane Johnson, *New York Review of Books*, November 10, 1977.

⁴Toni Morrison, *Song of Solomon* (New York: Knopf, 1977).

⁵"Running Away to Home—A Story Pattern in Children's Literature," *Language Arts* 55, 4 (April, 1978), 473.

⁶Culler, p. 15.

⁷"On Three Way of Writing for Children," *Children's Literature: Views and Reviews*, ed. Virginia Haviland (Chicago: Scott, Foresman, 1973), p. 236.

⁸Virginia Hamilton, *M. C. Higgins, the Great* (New York: Macmillan, 1974), p. 179.

⁹*The Sense of an Ending: Studies in the Theory of Fiction* (New York: Oxford, 1967), p. 52.